

On Fracture Characteristics of Particle-Dispersion Composites

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Summary

The fracture toughness of particle-dispersion composites, viz. SiC - epoxy composites, both static and dynamic, is investigated in correlation with the particle volume fraction resulting in the increase in K_{IC} and K_I^d with the increase in V_f for both cases, although there observe several wavy patterns. The increasing rate of K_I^d as a function of V_f is steeper than K_{IC} case, so K_{IC} and K_I^d finally almost coincide, although K_{IC} is far larger than K_I^d at $V_f = 0$. The fractography by use of a scanning electron microscope well explains the fracture toughness variation for both static and dynamic cases microscopically. That is, in the dynamic case, it was observed that the fracture surface was smooth and the crack advanced straight across the included SiC particles in a breakthrough manner. With the increase in V_f , K_I^d increases with the augmentation of SiC particle breaking, hence, requiring much more surface energy resulting in the steeper K_I^d gradient than in the static case.

Introduction

Understanding of fracture characteristics of particle-dispersion composites is necessary for their further and wider application, especially under dynamic condition.

Of course, there are works concerning these particle-dispersion composites, however, there still exist lots of points to be clarified, especially the fracture toughness, and the very dynamic fracture toughness is almost unexplored yet.

In the present report, the fracture toughness of particle-dispersion composites, both static and dynamic, is investigated in correlation with the particle volume fraction, and the fractography using a scanning electron microscope is also added.

Experimental

Test Specimen

The particle-dispersion composite specimens were made from SiC powders as particles and epoxy resin as a matrix, of which particle volume fraction ranging from zero to 40%. The property of this powder produced by Pacific Rundum Co., Japan is shown in Table I.

Table I. Property of SiC powders

20 μ	18	15	10	8	6	4	d(μ)
1%	3	17	55	72	86	96	1005
SiC	F.C	T.Fe	Al	F.Si	F.SiO ₂	PH	
99.3%	0.13	0.04	0.01	0.12	0.20	6.1	

The specimen is machined and its dimension is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Configuration and dimensions of specimen.

Fracture Toughness Measurement

The static fracture toughness, K_{IC} and the dynamic one were measured using a Charpy tester. A schematic diagram of the experimental measurement is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Schematic diagram for experimental measurement

In the course of loading, an impact blow was applied to the specimen in case of dynamic fracture toughness measurement, while for the static fracture measurement the same Charpy tester hammer was used by merely just giving a slight pressing on the specimen. All tests were done at room temperature.

Fractography

Fractographic observation was also performed on the fracture surfaces for both static and dynamic cases by use of a scanning electron microscope.

Fracture Toughness Presentation

When the impact load is applied near the crack tip, the stress in Y direction, σ_{YY} (Mode I) is given by the following Equation(1):

$$\sigma_{YY} = \frac{K_I(t)}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos\left(-\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left\{ 1 + \sin\left(-\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \sin\left(-\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) \right\} \quad (1)$$

Since $\theta = \pi/2$ and $r = y_0$ on Y axis, $K_I(t)$ is expressed as

$$K_I(t) = \sigma_{YY} \sqrt{2\pi y_0} \quad (2)$$

With the material linearity, σ_{YY} can be expressed by

$$\sigma_{YY} = E_Y^d \epsilon_Y^d \quad (3)$$

where E_Y^d is the dynamic Young's modulus and ϵ_Y^d is the dynamic strain.

Upon unstable fracture, the following term comes out.

$$K_I(t) = K_I^d \quad (4)$$

where K_I^d is the dynamic fracture toughness.

Inserting Equations (2) and (3) into Equation (4), the dynamic fracture toughness K_I^d is given by

$$K_I^d = E_Y^d \epsilon_Y^d \sqrt{2\pi y_0} \quad (5)$$

By the way, the initiation condition of unstable fracture under the

static loading is given by

$$K_I(t) = K_{IC} \quad (6)$$

where K_{IC} is the static fracture toughness.

In this case, it can be considered that the linearity shown in Equation (3) exists. The static fracture toughness K_{IC} is expressed by

$$K_{IC} = E_Y^S \epsilon_Y^S \sqrt{2\pi Y_0} \quad (7)$$

where E_Y^S is the static Young's modulus and ϵ_Y^S is the static strain.

Therefore, the static fracture toughness, K_{IC} and the dynamic fracture toughness, K_I^d can be determined by measuring the strains ϵ_Y^S and ϵ_Y^d in the Y axis through strain gages at the initiation of unstable fracture.

Experimental Results and Discussions

Fracture Toughness

Figures 3 and 4 present the variation of K_{IC} and K_I^d as a function of particle volume fraction V_f .

The solid line shown in Figures 3 and 4 is calculated by the following Equation (2) taking into account the composite influence at the crack tip.

$$K_{IC} = (K_{1C} - K_{2C})(1 - V_f)^{1/2} + K_{2C} \quad (\text{for static loading}). \quad (8)$$

where K_{1C} and K_{2C} are the fracture toughness of epoxy resin and sintered SiC, respectively.

In case of dynamic loading, supposing the same concept so that the relation between the dynamic fracture toughness K_I^d and V_f can be expressed by

$$K_I^d = (K_{1I}^d - K_{2I}^d)(1 - V_f)^{1/2} + K_{2I}^d \quad (\text{for dynamic loading}). \quad (9)$$

In view of Figures 3 and 4, roughly speaking, it is found that both K_{IC} and K_I^d decrease once but again increase with the increase in V_f . However, in case of static loading, the theoretical values given by Equation (8) always exceed those obtained by the experiment. On the contrary, in case of dynamic loading, K_I^d increases in accord with Equation (9).

From these results, it is observed that fracture toughness/ V_f gradient for the dynamic case is steeper than that of the static case, so that K_I^d almost coincides with K_{IC} at $V_f = 38\%$, even with rather large discrepancy of fracture toughness of about $0.5\text{MPam}^{1/2}$ at $V_f = 0$ between the static and the dynamic case.

Figure 3 - Variation of K_{IC} with V_f .

Figure 4 - Variation of K_I^d with V_f .

Fractographic Record

Figures 5(a) and 5(b) show the fracture surface near the initial notch tip at $V_f = 0$, where $K_{IC} \approx 1.0 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ for Figure 5(a) of static case and $K_{IC}^d \approx 0.5 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ for Figure 5(b) of dynamic case, respectively.

From these Figures, the unstable fracture in the static loading (Figure 5(a)) nearly initiates from one point and propagates accompanying a large tear line.

On the contrary, the unstable fracture in the dynamic loading (Figure 5(b)) initiates from many points. At the point of fracture origin many tear lines are observed on the fracture surface.

(a) $V_f = 0\%$, $K_{IC} \approx 1.0 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ (static) (b) $V_f = 0\%$, $K_{IC}^d \approx 0.5 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ (dynamic)

Figure 5 - Fracture surfaces near the initial notch tip.

These tendencies are nearly similar to those at $V_f = 10\%$. However, in case of the static loading, the unstable crack initiates at smaller K_{IC} compared to that of $V_f = 0$ as shown in Figure 3, while for the dynamic case shown in Figure 4 the K_{IC}^d values remain almost unchanged for $V_f = 0$ through $V_f = 10\%$.

In the high V_f range, it is found that the crack in the static loading initiates from many points as shown in Figure 5(c) ($V_f = 38\%$, $K_{IC} \approx 1.1 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$), similar to that in the dynamic loading as shown in Figure 5(d) ($V_f = 38\%$, $K_{IC}^d \approx 1.3 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$).

It seems that the particles behave themselves as defects in the composites specimen within the low particle volume fraction ranges.

The fracture surface morphology changes from large cleavagelike fracture surfaces to smaller ones or to smaller quasi-cleavagelike ones, with the increase in V_f , as seen from Figures 6(a) and 6(b). Particularly, in the dynamic loading as shown in Figure 6(b), the quasi-cleavagelike fracture surfaces are much observed more than the static

(c) $V_f = 38\%$, $K_{IC} \approx 1.1 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ (static) (d) $V_f = 38\%$, $K_I^d \approx 1.3 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ (dynamic)

Figure 5 - Fracture surfaces near the initial notch tip.

(a) $V_f = 38\%$, $K_{IC} \approx 1.1 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ (static) (b) $V_f = 38\%$, $K_I^d \approx 1.3 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ (dynamic)

Figure 6 - Fracture surfaces near the initial notch tip.

loading case shown in Figure 6(a).

This result would indicate that the crack growth from the stable fracture to the unstable fracture could be performed under the process of cutting particles directly.

Namely, K_I^d increases with the increase in V_f , because the particle augmentation makes more difficult for a crack to advance.

Young's Modulus

Figure 7 shows the relation between particle volume fractions, V_f and Young's modulus, E , where Young's modulus is measured by the strain gage applied on the specimen and a load cell as shown in Figure 8.

The specimen configuration is also shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7 - Relation between E and V_f .

Figure 8 - Specimen for E measurement (unit in mm).

As seen from Figure 7, Young's modulus increases remarkably depending on V_f . Furthermore, this tendency is independent of particle size.

In calculating K_{IC} and K_I^d , Young's modulus was assumed to be constant, irrespective of static or dynamic case, and the values shown in Figure 7 were used.

Conclusions

In order to clarify the fracture characteristics of particle-dispersion composites, the static fracture toughness, K_{IC} and the dynamic fracture toughness, K_{IC}^d are investigated for various particle volume fractions and discussed from the microscopic point of view.

- (1) The dynamic fracture toughness, K_{IC}^d increases remarkably depending on particle volume fraction, but not for the static fracture toughness, K_{IC} .
- (2) The dynamic fracture toughness, K_{IC}^d finally almost coincides with the static fracture toughness, K_{IC} at high particle volume fraction, say $V_f = 38\%$, so far as the present test results are concerned.
- (3) The particles in the dynamic loading make more difficult for a crack to advance than in the static loading.
- (4) Young's modulus increases with the increase in the particle volume fraction only, independent of particle size.

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